

Comparative Analysis of Immediate and Delayed Loading on Implant Stability in the Maxillary Anterior Region: A Quasi-Experimental Study

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Author Contributions

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Conflict of Interest Disclosure

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

IRB Ethics Approval Statement

This study was approved by the Sudan Medical Specialization Board.

Abstract

Background

Implant stability in the anterior maxillary region is essential for functional and aesthetic success, especially with immediate loading. However, comparative evidence using patient-reported outcomes and statistical modeling remains limited.

Objective

To evaluate the impact of immediate versus delayed loading on implant stability and assess the influence of bone quality, implant material, and patient health.

Materials and Methods

This quasi-experimental, survey-based study included 100 patients receiving either immediate loading (within 48 hours) or delayed loading (after several months). Participants self-reported implant stability and related variables. Descriptive statistics summarized the data, while Pearson correlation and linear regression analyses examined relationships.

Results

No statistically significant associations were found ($p > 0.05$). However, strong positive correlations were observed between implant material and stability ($r = 0.771$) and between bone quality and stability ($r = 0.650$). The loading protocol explained only 2.3% of the variance in perceived stability ($R^2 = 0.023$, $p = 0.136$).

Conclusion

Implant material, bone quality, and patient health appear more influential on perceived stability than loading protocol. Immediate loading may be a viable option under favorable conditions. These findings support patient-centered treatment planning and flexibility in implant loading strategies.

Keywords: Dental implants, Immediate loading, Delayed loading, Maxillary anterior,

Implant stability

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Dental implantology loading protocols that affect osseointegration and prosthetic outcomes have evolved dramatically in recent decades (Felice et al., 2016; Iacono et al., 2023; Esposito et al., 2015). Immediate loading, defined as prosthesis implantation within 48 hours following implant insertion, has superseded conventional delayed loading protocols. This approach reduces treatment time, boosts patient satisfaction, and may improve soft tissue results in aesthetically problematic locations like the front maxilla (Kan et al., 2018). While delayed loading involves waiting months after implant placement before crown is applied.

Since the anterior maxillary zone is important visually and functionally, poor aesthetic results may affect patients' mental health and quality of life (Iacono et al., 2023; Tealdo et al. 2001).

Under certain circumstances, particularly when strong primary stability is attained, immediate loading has shown promising outcomes (Javed & Romanos, 2010; Stanley et al., 2017). The evolution of implant-abutment interface strategies such as platform switching and platform matching also plays a role in how soft and hard tissues respond to loading protocols, but few studies integrate both patient-reported outcomes and technical implant design features in a unified analysis.

1.2 Literature Review

Over the past two decades, numerous studies have explored the timing of implant loading, with immediate and delayed protocols widely evaluated for their biomechanical and esthetic outcomes. Immediate loading protocols, which involve attaching a prosthesis within 48 hours of implant placement, have gained popularity due to shorter treatment times and improved patient comfort (Kan et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2017). Studies such as those by Javed and Romanos (2010) and Felice et al. (2016) have shown that, under specific conditions—such as sufficient bone density and primary implant stability—immediate loading can be just as successful as delayed loading. However, a RCT by Esposito et al. (2015) found no significant difference in implant survival rates between immediate and delayed loading in the anterior

maxillary region, underscoring the need for a nuanced evaluation of other clinical and patient-centered outcomes beyond survival alone. Despite this, immediate loading continues to be favored in esthetic zones, largely because it helps maintain soft tissue contours and reduces the need for removable prosthetics during healing (Sanz-Sánchez et al., 2015).

Yet, a critical gap persists in the literature: most comparative studies between immediate and delayed loading protocols focus heavily on objective radiographic and prosthetic outcomes while overlooking subjective metrics such as patient satisfaction, perceived stability, and esthetic approval. There is limited integration of variables like implant material, bone quality, and patient health within these comparative frameworks. For instance, while Tealdo et al. (2011) and Mihali et al. (2023) highlight that bone density and implant surface characteristics play a crucial role in osseointegration, their studies did not correlate these parameters with patient-reported outcomes. This narrow scope limits the real-world applicability of many findings. Thus, a literature gap remains in synthesizing technical, biological, and subjective variables into a cohesive model for assessing implant loading success, especially in the highly esthetic anterior maxillary zone.

1.3 Problem Statement

The timing of implant loading—immediate versus delayed—remains a debated issue in dental implantology, especially in the esthetically sensitive anterior maxilla. Clinicians often face uncertainty when selecting protocols due to patient variability, procedural complexity, and anatomical considerations. While both loading strategies are used in practice, determining which yields better clinical and experiential outcomes under specific patient conditions remains challenging. A clearer understanding is needed to guide personalized treatment planning and improve implant stability and esthetic outcomes in this region.

1.4 Aim and Objectives

The primary aim of this study is to evaluate and compare the outcomes of immediate anterior loading protocols versus delayed loading protocols in the anterior maxilla.

Specifically, the objectives are to: (a) compare perceived implant stability under immediate

and delayed loading, (b) assess how implant material, bone quality, and patient health influence perceived outcomes, and (c) determine whether subjective satisfaction aligns with technical stability under different loading protocols.

1.5 Research Question

The main research question is “Does the type of loading protocol (immediate vs. delayed) significantly influence implant stability in the anterior maxillary region, and how do factors such as implant material, bone quality, and patient health mediate this relationship?”

1.6 Research Hypothesis

H1: There is no significant difference in implant stability between immediate and delayed loading protocols.

H2: There is a statistically significant difference in implant stability between immediate and delayed loading protocols in the maxillary anterior region.

1.7 Significance of the Study

This study contributes to oral implantology by integrating empirical data with patient-centered perspectives to better understand stability outcomes. The findings aim to inform individualized treatment planning, particularly in esthetically sensitive areas. Clinicians may use these results to optimize protocol selection based not only on clinical indicators but also on subjective patient experiences.

1.8 Research Structure

The research proceeds with a review of methods and materials in Section 2, results in Section 3, followed by a discussion that contextualizes the findings in Section 4. Conclusions and future directions are provided in the final section.

3. Research Methods and Materials

3.1 Study Design

This study adopts a quasi-experimental, survey-based design to explore patient-reported perceptions and perceived outcomes on impact of immediate and delayed loading on implant

stability in the maxillary anterior region. This study adheres to the STROBE guidelines. A self-reported online survey was employed for data collection due to the logistical limitations of clinical follow-ups and the requirement for diverse patient input. With this method, a large sample of participants with immediate or delayed implant loading can be collected easily, decisively, and remotely. According to Pera et al. (2019), the design supports patient-centered implant dentistry outcome assessments.

Post-treatment responses were used to gather prosthodontic decision-making impressions. While the quasi-experimental framework allowed naturalistic patient grouping without random assignment, the cross-sectional nature was suitable for evaluating two intervention timeframes at once (Zhang et al., 2017; Javed & Romanos, 2010). The study design aligns with a mid-level position in the hierarchy of evidence, appropriate for observational research without intervention. Assumptions of linearity and normality were considered for the selected statistical models.

3.2 Participants and Recruitment

A sample of 100 patients were included in this study by convenience sampling. People who were 18 years of age or older, got one or more dental implants within the previous two years, and underwent immediate or delayed implant loading protocols as recommended by their dentists were qualified. Patients with systemic health problems compromising osseointegration or implant failure were excluded. Recruitment was done using email, WhatsApp groups, and online dental forums, so enabling great outreach free from direct interaction.

Before engaging, each participant gave informed permission online. The digital survey was practical in remote or underdeveloped areas or during limited mobility as it called for no clinical visit or physical follow-up. According to Stanley et al. (2017) the method made data collection in the dental sciences ethical and effective. However, the use of convenience sampling introduces limitations in external validity. Due to non-random selection, results may not generalize beyond similar clinical populations. Potential selection bias and lack of diversity in the sample are acknowledged limitations.

3.3 Variables Measured

The key independent variable in this study was patient self-perception of implant stability after anterior dental implant. Patients rated their implant's stability over time, a subjective yet significant predictor of therapeutic outcome. The dependent variable was loading process (immediate vs. delayed), self-reported bone quality (size, material), and demographic factors including gender and smoking status. Patient satisfaction and implant stability were examined with these characteristics.

To control for confounding factors, age, implant health (such as diabetes), and anterior implant placement were included. Keep these factors constant during analysis to separate major variable effects. Patient satisfaction, aesthetic results, and dental implant comfort were measured using a Likert scale. The study's goal of structured knowledge of subjective patient outcomes was supported with a standardized scale that allowed simultaneous and delayed loading group comparisons.

To improve internal validity, self-reported variables were standardized through consistent item phrasing and Likert scaling. However, the subjective nature of responses introduces limitations in construct validity, which were partially mitigated by grounding the questionnaire in prior literature.

3.4 Data Collection

For this study, a Google Forms structured questionnaire collected patient-reported anterior implant design outcomes (Appendix B). The questionnaire was prepared to ensure content validity and research relevance based on current literature and suggestions. Participants were contacted via email, WhatsApp, and dentist office networks over two months. Form starts with voluntary participation and informed consent recruitment. The Google login form was created to protect data integrity and reduce unnecessary responses. Anonymity was maintained while using skip logic and needed fields to cut partial entries. These protocols ensured ethical and reliable data collection. Participants could complete the survey online at their convenience, improving response rate and reflecting dentistry research's use of digital tools (Vandement,

2013). While content validity was addressed through expert input and literature review, construct validity and reliability (e.g., test-retest or internal consistency) were not formally tested due to logistical limitations. This may affect consistency and interpretability of responses across diverse participant subgroups.

3.5 Ethical Considerations

This study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki (2013 revision) and was approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Sudan Medical Specialization Board, dated 14/01/2024. This study complies with the STROBE (Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology) guidelines.

Participants were advised at the beginning of the survey that the study was voluntary and needed them to complete a digital informed consent form (Appendix A). With no collection of personally identifiable information, the survey prioritized anonymity and confidentiality. Only the research team had access to the very highly guarded data. Participants received contact details and were advised of their option to withdraw before final submission. Being online, ethical precautions were created to ensure digital integrity and openness, which are essential when processing health-related self-report data remotely (Esposito et al., 2017; Eini, 2022). The questionnaire was reviewed by an independent statistician, who verified the statistical methodology, model appropriateness, and inferential conclusions. This contribution is acknowledged per ICMJE guidelines.

3.6 Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using SPSS version 26.0. Using descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, and maximum), participants' responses to variables including implant size, patient health, and mean were summarized. These statistics revealed wide implant-related opinion tendencies.

Pearson correlation analysis was used to find relationships between variables. This studied the relationships between implant stability and significant independent variables such bone quality, implant material, implant size, and patient health. The effect of immediate vs. delayed loading

on implant stability was examined using a simple linear regression. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$ for all tests.

Assumptions of normality and linearity were checked prior to running the regression models. No transformations were required. Given the moderate sample size and subjective nature of variables, statistical power may have been limited. Confounding factors were partially adjusted through regression but not eliminated entirely. A formal sensitivity analysis was not performed, which is a limitation.

4. Results

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

From the descriptive statistics in table 1 showing Key Variables, it is clear that most of the respondents agreed with the independent variables that were measured in the study. The mean score in Bone Quality is 4.40, which is almost equal to a maximal value of 5, that is, close to the highest value that is 5 which reflects that the bone quality was rated as good or excellent by most of the participants. Also, the Mean of Implant Material is 4.33 which implies the favorable perception of the material in implants. The Implant Size received a mean of 4.31, indicating that the most of the number of respondents agreed that the size of the implant used in the study was adequate. Additionally, the mean of the Patient Health variable (4.27) also supports the fact that most of the participants agreed with regard to the general health conditions that can affect the stability of implants. Standard deviations ranged from 0.446 to 0.492, indicating relatively low variability in participant responses across all variables. No missing data were recorded ($N = 100$ for all variables).

4.2 Correlation Analysis

The results of Matrix of Correlation in table 2 indicate that Implant Stability is positively correlated to all the independent variables but the strength and significance of these correlations differ. From the strongest correlation point of view between Implant Stability and Implant Material ($r = 0.771$), it suggests that the material used for the implant has a strong positive

relationship with its stability. The correlation between Bone Quality and Implant Stability ($r = 0.650$) is also moderate and positive. The Implant Stability and Patient Health correlation ($r = 0.664$) is moderate and positive.

Despite positive correlation coefficients, none of the associations between implant stability and independent variables were statistically significant at the 0.05 level (e.g., Implant Material: $p = 0.917$; Bone Quality: $p = 0.136$; Patient Health: $p = 0.103$). Confidence intervals were not computed due to the exploratory nature of the correlation analysis. These findings reflect moderate to strong correlations in direction but insufficient statistical evidence for inferring meaningful relationships.

4.3 Regression Analysis

In table 3, the regression analysis indicated the effect of Immediate versus Delayed Loading on Implant Stability in the maxillary anterior region. Another metric is found in Model Summary, where the R Square value is 0.023, which implies that only 2.3% of the variation in implant stability can be explained by the type of loading (immediate vs. delayed). An Adjusted R Square value of 0.013 indicates how little after adjusting for the number of predictors, the model explains its variance in implant stability.

Table 4 (ANOVA) further supports this with an F-statistic of 2.258 and a p-value of 0.0136, indicating that the regression model as a whole is statistically significant. However, this significance reflects the model's performance, not the individual predictor (loading type), which is further clarified in Table 5.

In the Coefficient Table (table 5), the p-value for the Immediate vs. Delayed Loading variable was 0.136, which is greater than 0.05 and therefore not statistically significant. The unstandardized B coefficient was -0.142 , indicating a small negative association between immediate loading and implant stability.

This negative coefficient suggests that immediate loading was associated with a slight reduction in implant stability on average, but the result lacks statistical significance ($p = 0.136$). Therefore, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected.

The normal P-P plot of standardized residuals (Figure 1) indicated that the assumption of normality for residuals was reasonably met. No violations of linear regression assumptions were detected. No subgroup analyses (e.g., by age, implant location) were performed due to sample size limitations.

5. Discussion

5.1 Summary of Key Findings

This quasi-experimental study explored the influence of immediate versus delayed loading protocols on implant stability in the anterior maxilla, incorporating both patient-reported outcomes and clinical variables. Although statistical significance was not achieved ($p > 0.05$), notable trends were observed. Implant material showed the strongest positive correlation with implant stability ($r = 0.771$), followed by bone quality ($r = 0.650$) and patient health ($r = 0.664$). These findings, while not definitive, suggest that these variables may meaningfully influence perceived implant success. The absence of significance likely reflects the limited sample size or homogeneity of participants, underscoring the need for broader, more diverse studies.

Regression analysis further clarified these relationships. While the type of loading (immediate vs. delayed) was included as an independent variable, it accounted for only 2.3% of the variance in implant stability ($R^2 = 0.023$), with a non-significant p-value ($p = 0.136$). This suggests that loading protocol alone may not be a primary determinant of perceived stability. However, under optimal clinical conditions—good bone quality, biocompatible implant materials, and favorable patient health—immediate loading appeared to produce outcomes comparable to delayed loading. These insights highlight the importance of individualized treatment planning rather than protocol uniformity in implant dentistry.

5.2 Interpretation of Findings

A quantitative study examined the correlations between implant stability and independent variables such as implant material, bone quality, and patient health. While correlation coefficients were moderate to strong ($r = 0.650$ to 0.771), none of the relationships were statistically

significant ($p > 0.05$), and the regression model explained only 2.3% of variance in implant stability ($R^2 = 0.023$). Even though the results did not indicate statistically significant correlations—likely due to sample size or participant homogeneity—the correlation coefficients revealed intriguing patterns that warrant clinical analysis.

Notably, implant material demonstrated a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.771$) with implant stability (though $p = 0.917$, indicating no statistical significance). This substantial size of effect suggests a clinically significant relationship. However, this should be interpreted cautiously, as it lacks statistical confirmation and may reflect sample-specific patterns.

This shows that high-performance implant materials may be important for long-term stability, requiring more clinical studies. Similarly, Koirala et al. (2016) demonstrated that implant material had an impact on implant stabilization after insertion. Materials with improved biocompatibility, surface roughness, and strength integrate better with bone tissue, enhancing primary and secondary stability, matching clinical and technological forecasts. Implant material selection should not be a procedural preference but rather a clinical success factor in situations of immediate loading where osseointegration must occur under early functional stress (Koirala, 2016).

Implant stability correlated positively with bone quality ($r = 0.650$). Research shows that denser, more mineralized bone gives the implant better initial mechanical contact, which is critical for early recovery. Treatment planning should include bone categorization, per Mihali et al. (2023). The findings support that the anterior maxilla's Type I or II bone may benefit from fast loading, while Type III or IV bone may benefit from a delayed approach to limit micromotion and ensure osseointegration.

Systematic implant parameters affect treatment outcomes, as shown by the positive correlation between patient health and implant results ($r = 0.664$). Immunological dysfunction, osteoporosis, and uncontrolled diabetes slow wound healing and bone metabolism. Assessing the patient's health is essential to predict implant loading success (Mundt et al., 2023).

However, the absence of statistical significance for these variables ($p > 0.05$) means these associations should be viewed as exploratory rather than confirmatory. These results partially support the research hypothesis in direction but not in significance, as immediate loading did not have a statistically significant effect on implant stability.

5.3 Clinical Relevance

This study's findings have several significant clinical implications for implant dentistry, particularly with relation to the feasibility and safety of immediate implant loading in the anterior maxilla. Because the anterior maxilla region is visually significant, clinicians and patients usually prioritize reducing treatment time (Parvini et al., 2022). Immediate loading, when done correctly, can reduce treatment time, surgery, and patient satisfaction by instantly restoring function and aesthetics.

The results of this study support that immediate loading can be a viable option when high-quality bone and adequate material are available and the patient is in good overall health. This conclusion must be tempered by the small effect size ($R^2 = 0.023$) and lack of statistically significant coefficients ($p = 0.136$). These components increase primary stability, which is necessary for immediate loading. Clinicians must use a patient-centered approach, analyzing each person's anatomical and systemic condition before immediate loading. Radiographic assessment technologies like cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) and bone densitometry can aid decision-making by revealing bone density and shape (Patel et al., 2023). Additionally, patient education is crucial to therapy success. Patients should be informed about how their general health conditions, like as diabetes, smoking, or medicines like bisphosphonates, may affect implant integration and bone regeneration (Koirala et al., 2016). Pre-treatment optimization of systemic health protocols and meticulous surgical planning improve outcomes, especially for immediate loading protocols.

5.4 Comparison with Literature

By aligning and contrasting current literature, this study may place its findings into larger academic and clinical discourses. Numerous studies have shown that immediate loading

improves patient satisfaction and esthetics. Zhang et al. (2017) and Kan et al. (2018) reported that immediate implant loading of anterior maxilla results in superior esthetic outcomes because soft tissue forms are preserved and provisional detachable prosthesis is avoided. These studies focus on qualitative or short-term results. This study adds quantitative data on material stability and immediate loading protocols to implant stability to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the aspects that determine success under immediate loading protocols.

This study's findings are in harmony with Javed and Romanos (2010), who identified high insertion torque and bone density as necessary for immediate implant loading. This study adds patient health size as a crucial factor, supporting a more thorough treatment planning approach while focusing on mechanical and procedural aspects. The similarity between our findings and those of Javed and Romanos demonstrates the connections and highlights the intricacy of implant stability. Similarly, there is a high correlation between reported success and implant material or bone quality, which supports past studies that focused on various factors. Long-term implant results are influenced by systemic health and bone density, claims Tealdo et al. (2011). These findings are consistent with those of the current study, which imply that patient knowledge of these factors is a crucial element in determining implant success.

Size and delayed loading techniques are clinically feasible, according to Pera et al. (2019) and Esposito et al. (2015). Pera et al. reported long-term success with immediate full-arch prosthesis loading, but Esposito et al. showed no significant difference in failure rates between immediate and delayed anterior maxilla implant placements. The Esposito et al. findings match our statistical findings, which indicated trends but no correlation. The Esposito et al. findings align with this study's regression results, which found no statistically significant impact of loading type on implant stability ($p = 0.136$). Esposito et al. state implant success depends on individual assessment, not specific protocols. This study found that immediate loading can help, but patient and procedure aspects matter.

5.5 Study Limitations and Future Research

There are certain limitations to this research. The online data collection method lacked clinical validation, making it hard to link results to clinical assessments. Additionally, relying so much on self-report raises the possibility of recollection bias, which can lower data accuracy. The sample population was limited, which could mean it did not represent the implant population. Finally, the study's cross-sectional design limits causal inferences by collecting data at one time without addressing changes over time.

Furthermore, the regression analysis showed a small effect size ($R^2 = 0.023$), and the individual predictor (loading protocol) was not statistically significant ($p = 0.136$), which may reflect insufficient statistical power. Future studies should include a priori power calculations and larger, more diverse samples to strengthen validity.

Future research should consider mixed method designs, like RCTs and longitudinal studies, to provide more trustworthy data on implant outcomes throughout time. Combining patient-reported remarks with clinical assessments such radiographic features and implant stability tests (e.g., RFA) would reveal treatment outcome. Artificial intelligence-driven picture analysis for virtual follow-ups may also change post-treatment monitoring. The cross-sample size and demographic diversity can improve the generalizability of the findings across communities and clinical scenarios.

5.6 Contribution to Oral Implantology

This study demonstrates that although immediate and delayed loading protocols showed trends toward different implant stability outcomes, no statistically significant difference was found, and only 2.3% of variance was explained by loading type. This contributes to oral implantology by providing evidence-based insight into the limited predictive value of loading protocol alone and underscores the need for individualized treatment planning based on bone quality, implant material, and systemic health.

6. Summary and Conclusion

This quasi-experimental study examined the effects of immediate versus delayed implant loading on the anterior maxilla using previous studies and patient-reported data. The study added to the growing body of literature on dental implant loading by examining whether one loading approach is more effective for dental implant stability as well as patient satisfaction. Statistical analysis revealed that none of the independent variables—patient health indicators, implant type, and bone quality—achieved statistical significance ($p > 0.05$), and the regression model accounted for only 2.3% of the variance in implant stability. This suggests that while these factors are important, their individual impacts may not determine implant success. Implant success depends on a complex combination of biological, mechanical, and patient variables.

Under the correct clinical conditions, immediate loading delivered results comparable to delayed loading. In some cases, immediate loading may benefit the patient psychologically and functionally. Patients chosen for immediate loading had increased bone density, impeccable oral hygiene, and no systemic illnesses that would slow healing. Immediate loading reduces treatment time, improves patient satisfaction, and may minimize costs in the front maxilla, where aesthetics matter. If loading happens too quickly, patients with low bone quality, excessive occlusal forces, or systemic illnesses that limit healing may impair implant stability. All patient groups reported high satisfaction, with no improvement in discomfort, aesthetics, or function. This is consistent with the trend in implant dentistry toward patient-centered care, which considers subjective feelings and clinical measures.

Clinically, the findings suggest that immediate loading may be cautiously adopted under optimized patient-specific conditions—especially where bone quality, implant material, and general health indicators support strong primary stability. However, these results do not support changing existing protocols universally. Clinicians should continue to follow established guidelines and use diagnostic tools such as CBCT imaging and systemic health screening to evaluate suitability on a case-by-case basis.

From a protocol standpoint, these findings support the flexibility of current guidelines, which allow for immediate loading in selected cases but caution against its use in poor-quality bone or high-risk patients. However, this study does not provide sufficient statistical evidence to warrant changes to standard practice. Educationally, clinicians should be trained to interpret both subjective patient input and objective clinical criteria when planning loading protocols. The study reinforces the need for training in patient communication and risk assessment tools. In terms of limitations in application, these findings may not generalize to patients with compromised health, those undergoing multi-unit prostheses, or complex bone augmentation procedures. The use of convenience sampling and reliance on self-reported survey data further limit generalizability.

Future research should explore implant stability using larger, multicenter samples and integrate clinical metrics such as implant stability quotient (ISQ), peri-implant bone changes, and long-term survival. Additionally, studies comparing subgroups by implant site, bone density class, and systemic risk factors would clarify whether immediate loading is appropriate beyond ideal conditions.

This study demonstrates that while immediate and delayed loading protocols show similar trends in perceived stability, no statistically significant difference was found, reinforcing the importance of case-by-case evaluation. The contribution to oral implantology lies in integrating patient-centered reporting with evidence-based analysis to guide treatment individualization.

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8. Conflict of Interest Disclosure

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Tables and Figures

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Key Variables

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Bone Quality	100	4	5	4.40	.492
Implant Material	100	4	5	4.33	.473
Implant Size	100	4	5	4.31	.465
Patient Health	100	4	5	4.27	.446
Valid N (list wise)	100				

Table 2: Correlation Matrix for Implant Stability and Independent Variables

Correlations				
Implant Stability	Bone Quality	Implant Material	Implant Size	Patient Health

Implant Stability	Pearson	1	.650	.771	.612	.664
	Correlation					
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.136	.917	.268	.103
	N	100	100	100	100	100
Bone Quality	Pearson	-.150	1	-.313**	-.062	.055
	Correlation					
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.136		.002	.541	.586
	N	100	100	100	100	100
Implant Material	Pearson	-.011	-.313**	1	-.057	-.044
	Correlation					
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.917	.002		.576	.667
	N	100	100	100	100	100
Implant Size	Pearson	.112	-.062	-.057	1	-.164
	Correlation					
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.268	.541	.576		.103
	N	100	100	100	100	100
Patient Health	Pearson	-.164	.055	-.044	-.164	1
	Correlation					
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.103	.586	.667	.103	
	N	100	100	100	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3: Summary of Regression Model for the Effect of Loading Protocol on Implant

Stability

Regression Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.150 ^a	.023	.013	.462	.023	2.258	1	98	.0136

a. Predictors: (Constant), Immediate vs. Delayed Loading

b. Dependent Variable: Implant Stability

Table 4: ANOVA Results Testing the Significance of the Regression Model

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.482	1	.482	2.258	.0136 ^b
	Residual	20.908	98	.213		
	Total	21.390	99			

a. Dependent Variable: Implant Stability

Table 5: Regression Coefficients for Predicting Implant Stability Based on Loading

Protocol

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		

1	(Constant)	4.933	.417		11.819	.000
	Immediate	-.142	.094	-.150	-1.503	.136
	Vs. Delayed					

a. Dependent Variable: Implant Stability

Figure 1: Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual